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Research Article

The Impact of Exposure Time and Fumigation Intensity of Dhoopa on Indoor Microbial Load

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ABSTRACT

Airborne microorganisms, including potentially pathogenic species, are widely present in the environment and require effective control measures. Traditional fumigation practices such as Havana and Dhoopa fumigation have been used for centuries to lower microbial contamination and reduce the risk of infection. In this study, two Dhoopa Formulations (DF-I and DF-II) were developed using natural ingredients with known antimicrobial properties—cow ghee, camphor, neem leaves and bark, drumstick leaves and bark, mustard seeds, and Guggul resin. To assess fumigation intensity, different concentrations of Dhoopa (2 g, 4 g, 6 g, 8 g, 10 g, and 12 g) were tested at exposure times ranging from 1 to 5 hours, in a closed room of 1000 cubic feet using an electric burner and antimicrobial efficacy was evaluated by quantifying bacterial and fungal colony-forming units (CFU) in indoor air. The maximum fumigation effect was observed at the 10 g concentration at 4 hr. To assess the effect of exposure duration, fumigation with Dhoopa Formulations (DF-I and DF-II) was carried out separately in a closed room of 1000 cubic feet. Both formulations produced highly significant ($p < 0.001$), time-dependent reductions in microbial counts, with the strongest activity observed at the 4th hour using a 10 g concentration. DF-I achieved a 96.30% fumigation effect in bacterial colonies and 95.20% in fungal colonies, while DF-II exhibited 93.00% fumigation effect in bacterial colonies and 95.83% in fungal colonies. These results indicate that both formulations maintain strong antimicrobial efficacy, with maximum microbial load reduction at 4 hours, demonstrating their effectiveness for prolonged indoor air disinfection.

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INTRODUCTION

The environment is home to billions of microorganisms, and exposure through inhalation of contaminated air increases susceptibility to airborne diseases. Microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites are responsible for transmitting a wide range of illnesses, posing a serious threat to human health [1]. The presence of these pathogens in ambient air highlights the need for effective methods of disinfection and sterilization, which remain a major concern [2]. In Indian mythology, Havana and Dhoopa fumigation practices have long been performed to reduce microbial loads to safer levels and prevent disease. However, modern synthetic sterilization methods, such as formalin gas fumigation, can cause occupational hazards and even potential carcinogenic effects in exposed groups [3]. This has created an urgent need for safer alternatives in infection control. Ayurveda describes *Dhoopana Karma* as an age-old practice where fumigation with medicinal plant-based materials is used for environmental purification [4]. Historically, fumigation has been incorporated into rituals like *Homa* and *Havana*, in which herbal substances are combusted, and the generated smoke helps disinfect vulnerable spaces [5,6,7]. While many herbal agents possess intrinsic antimicrobial activity, their combination is thought to enhance efficacy through synergistic effects [8]. Two critical but underexplored factors in fumigation are fumigation intensity and exposure time. Fumigation intensity refers to the concentration or dose of herbal material released per unit volume of air, while exposure time is the duration microbes remain in contact with the fumigant [9,10]. Research on chemical fumigants shows that microbial inactivation generally follows a dose–time pattern: higher doses and longer exposures increase microbial kill rates, though safety limits must be considered. Similar

quantitative studies are lacking for herbal fumigants like *Dhoopa*. Evidence from chemical fumigants such as ethyl formate and formic acid further emphasizes the importance of studying both concentration and duration [11]. Addressing this gap, the present study investigates how varying Dhoopa intensity ($\text{g}\cdot\text{ft}^{-3}$) and exposure time affect bacterial and fungal reduction in indoor air. Fumigation experiments were performed in a standardized 1000-cubic-foot enclosed space using an electric burner [12]. For this purpose, two herbal formulations, DF-I and DF-II, were developed using cow's ghee, camphor, and plant-derived materials including neem (*Azadirachta indica*), drumstick (*Moringa oleifera*), mustard seeds (*Brassica juncea*), and guggul resin (*Commiphora wightii*). These ingredients, long recognized in Ayurveda for their aromatic and antimicrobial properties, were combined to create a natural, safe, and cost-effective air-sanitizing alternative to chemical fumigants [13]. This study evaluates the effectiveness of the formulations by analyzing microbial load reduction under varying fumigation intensities and exposure times, providing scientific evidence for their potential as natural air sanitizers

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection and Certification of Plant Materials

Plant materials, such as Neem leaves and bark (*Azadirachta indica*) and Drumstick leaves and bark (*Moringa oleifera*) were collected from a medicinal garden at Jiwaji University campus. The identification of the plant materials was confirmed by a taxonomist from the CSIR–National Institute of Science Communication. Following identification, the plant materials were screened for quality before being used for preparation of the herbal Dhoopa. Cow's ghee, guggul, camphor, and mustard yellow seeds were also collected from the local market as additional materials.

2.2 Preparation of Dhoopa formulations

Dhoopa formulations were prepared using leaves and bark of Drumstick (*Moringa oleifera*), leaves and bark of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Guggul (*Commiphora wightii*), mustard yellow seeds (*Brassica juncea*), camphor (*Cinnamomum camphora*), and cow's ghee. Initially, the plant

materials were cleaned with running tap water, dried in the shade, and ground into a moderately coarse powder, which was then passed through a 60-mesh sieve. All ingredients were taken in equal proportions and thoroughly mixed. The formulation details are provided in Table 1 and Fig. 1.

Table 1 Ingredients Dhoopa Formulations (DF-I and DF-II)

S. No.	Herbal Ingredients	Plant part used in DF-I	Plant part used in DF-II	Quantity
1	Drumstick (<i>Moringa oleifera</i>)	Leaves	Bark	10 ml
2	Neem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>)	Leaves	Bark	10 gm
3	Guggul (<i>Commiphora wightii</i>)	Gum-resin	Gum-resin	10 gm
4	Mustard yellow (<i>Brassica juncea</i>)	Seeds	Seeds	10 gm
5	Camphor (<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i>)	Dried powder	Dried powder	10 gm
6	Cows Ghee	Ghee	Ghee	10 gm

Fig. 1 Ingredients of DF-I and DF-II

2.3 Fumigation Method

A room of 1000 cubic feet was fumigated by burning varying concentrations of *Dhoopa* (2 g, 4 g, 6 g, 8 g, 10 g, and 12 g) using an electric burner, after which the room was sealed. Air sampling was carried out before fumigation and subsequently at 1-hour intervals up to the 5th hour. To assess the effect of exposure time, 10 g of each *Dhoopa* formulation (DF-I and DF-II) was applied separately in the same room, with exposure durations ranging from 1 to 10 hrs., as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Fumigation with Electric Burner

2.4 Media Preparation

Nutrient Agar (NA, 28 g/1000 mL) and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA, 65 g/1000 mL; Hi-Media) were prepared by dissolving the respective media

in distilled water, followed by complete heating. Media were autoclaved for 15 minutes at 121°C to maintain 15 psi pressure, cooled to 45–50°C, and aseptically poured into sterile Petri dishes under a laminar air flow cabinet Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Petri plates Preparation

2.5 Collection of Air Samples Before and After Fumigation

Nutrient agar (NA) and Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) media were prepared for quantitative analysis of bacterial and fungal load, respectively. Fungal and bacterial samples were collected from the center of the room, placed on agar plates, followed by the passive settle plate technique at the time intervals. Both the pre- and post-fumigation sampling followed the standard method of the 1/1/1 schedule (Petri dishes left open to the air for 1 hr., 1 meter above the floor, and 1 meter from the wall/any obstacle) to obtain the appropriate surface density for counting the load for the time of exposure. Following exposure, collected samples were sealed with Para film, incubated in an upside-down position NA plates at 37°C for 24 hours for bacterial enumeration, and SDA plates at 25°C for 2 days for fungal enumeration^[14].

2.6 Assessment of Microbial Load

Air sampling was performed before fumigation and at hourly intervals post-fumigation. After

incubation, bacterial and fungal colonies were enumerated as colony-forming units (CFU). The microbial load in indoor air (CFU/m³) was calculated for both pre- and post-fumigation samples using Omeliansky's equation^[15].

$$N = \frac{5a \times 10^4}{bt^{-1}}$$

Where N = Indoor air microbes in CFU/m³, a = Colonies number per Petri dish, b = surface area of dish (cm²), and t = Time of exposure (minutes).

3. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of the intensity of fumigation (concentration of Dhoopa) and the exposure time of the Dhoopa Formulations (DF-I and DF-II) to evaluate percentage of Fumigation Effect or Mean Reduction of bacterial and fungal colony count CFU/m³ during different set of experiments with time intervals was done by One-Way ANOVA with post hoc analysis by Dunnett's test to compare the mean of all controls to the means of all treatments with time intervals through GraphPad Prism Version 8.0.2 (263) and MS Excel 2019.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Impact of Fumigation Intensity (Conc.) of Dhoopa on indoor Bacterial and Fungal load

The fumigation intensity of Dhoopa was evaluated through Fumigation at different concentrations (2 g, 4 g, 6 g, 8 g, 10 g, and 12 g) in a 1000 cubic feet area of room, demonstrating a significant reduction statistically ($P < 0.001$) in both bacterial and fungal colony counts (CFU/m³). Pre-fumigation controls showed a mean bacterial colony count of 428.0±19.0 CFU/m³ and a fungal colony count of 192.1±11.6 CFU/m³. Following Dhoopa treatment, bacterial counts progressively decreased to 161.6±15.7 (1st hr.), 96.1±11.6 (2nd

hr.), 52.4±7.6 (3rd hr.), 34.9±4.4CFU/m³ (4th hr.), and 65.5±7.6CFU/m³ (5th hr.), representing the highest reduction at 4th hr. (fumigation effect 92.26%). Similarly, fungal counts declined to 109.2±4.4 (1st hr.), 78.6±7.6 (2nd hr.), 39.3±7.6 (3rd hr.), 8.7±4.4CFU/m³ (4th hr.), and 17.5±8.6CFU/m³ (5th hr.), achieving the highest reduction at 4th hr. with 10g of Dhoopa concentration (fumigation effect 95.00%) as shown in Table 2, Table 3, and Fig.4.

Table 2 Impact of Fumigation Intensity (Conc.) of Dhoopa on Bacterial load

Impact of Fumigation Intensity (Conc.) of Dhoopa						
Viable Bacterial load CFU/m ³ (Mean ± SEM)						
Fumigation Intensity (Conc. of Dhoopa)	Control	1 st hr.	2 nd hr.	3 rd hr.	4 th hr.	5 th hr.
2 g	397.5±26.6	253.3±19.1	183.4±15.1	131±7.6	100.4±11.6	122.3±11.6
4 g	393.1±20.1	310±19.1	200.9±8.7	152±11.5	74.23.4±11.5	152.3±23.11
6 g	493.5±34.1	318.9±30.6	262.1±20.0	170±20.0	91.7±7.6	165.9±8.7
8 g	559.0±48.6	283.9±11.6	209.9±15.1	157.2±15.1	87.3±15.7	139.7±11.6
10 g	428.0±19.0	161.6±15.7	96.1±11.6	52.4±7.6	34.9±4.4	65.5±7.6
12 g	375±28.6	174.7±11.6	131.0±15.1	87.3±11.6	39.6±4.4	69.9±4.4

Table 3 Impact of Fumigation Intensity (Conc.) of Dhoopa on Fungal load

Impact of Fumigation Intensity (Conc.) of Dhoopa						
Viable Fungal load CFU/m ³ (Mean ± SEM)						
Fumigation Intensity (Conc. of Dhoopa)	Control	1 st hr.	2 nd hr.	3 rd hr.	4 th hr.	5 th hr.
2 g	87.33±11.6	74.23±11.6	52.4±7.6	30.57±4.4	30.57±8.7	34.93±4.4
4 g	187.8±15.74	179.0±4.4	131.0±7.6	39.3±4.6	56.8±4.4	69.9±4.4
6 g	117.9±7.6	91.7±7.6	69.9±11.6	61.1±8.7	34.9±8.7	61.1±4.4
8 g	336.3±15.7	196±7.6	117.9±7.6	69.9±4.4	48.0±4.4	65.5±7.6
10 g	192.1±11.6	109.2±4.4	78.6±7.6	39.3±7.6	8.7±4.4	17.5±8.6
12 g	179.0±11.6	117.9±15.1	74.2±11.6	26.2±7.6	8.7±4.4	17.5±4.4

Fig. 4 Intensity of Dhoopa through Fumigation at different concentrations (2 g, 4 g, 6 g, 8 g, 10 g, and 12 g) in 1000 cubic feet area of room, demonstrating a Reduction of Mean Viable Bacterial and Fungal Colony Count CFU/m³ and Fumigation Effect of Dhoopa, Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM; *p<0.05; **p<0.002; *p < 0.001, Dhoopa fumigation effect significant from 1sthr. to 5thhr. by repeated measures, One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s multiple comparisons test.**

4.2 Impact of Exposure Time (1 to 10 hours) of Dhoopa Formulation-I (DF-I) on Bacterial Load

The Impact of Exposure Time of Dhoopa Formulation-I (DF-I) was evaluated through Fumigation with different Time Intervals (1 to 10 hrs.) in a 1000 cubic feet area of room, demonstrating a significant reduction statistically (P < 0.001) in both bacterial and fungal colony counts (CFU/m³). Pre-fumigation controls showed a mean bacterial colony count of 1782.0±30.3 CFU/m³ and a fungal colony count of 91.7±7.6 CFU/m³. Following Dhoopa treatment, bacterial counts progressively decreased to 611.4±19.0 (1st

hr.), 476.1±26.6 (2nd hr.), 310.1±43.0 (3rd hr.), 65.5±7.6 CFU/m³ (4th hr.), 100.4±11.6 (5th hr.), 139.7±15.7 (6th hr.), 179.0±11.6 (7th hr.), 196.5±7.6 (8th hr.), 214.0±15.7 (9th hr.) and, 231.5±11.6 (10th hr.) CFU/m³. Representing the highest reduction at 4th hr. (fumigation effect 96.30%). Similarly, fungal counts declined to 61.1±4.4 (1st hr.), 30.6±4.4 (2nd hr.), 13.1±0.0 (3rd hr.), 4.4±4.4 CFU/m³ (4th hr.), 8.7±14.4 CFU/m³ (5th hr.), 13.1±0.0 CFU/m³ (6th hr.), 13.1±0.0 CFU/m³ (7th hr.), 17.5±4.4 CFU/m³ (8th hr.), 17.5±4.4 CFU/m³ (9th hr.) and 17.5±4.4 CFU/m³ (10th hr.) achieving the highest reduction at 4th hr. (fumigation effect 95.20%). as shown in Table 4, Fig.5 Graph (A) & (B), Fig.7.

Table 4 Impact of Exposure Time (1 to 10 hours) of DF-I on Bacterial and Fungal Load

Fumigating Agent Dhoopa Formulation (DF-I)											
Viable Bacterial load CFU/m ³ (Mean ± SEM)											
Sample Site (1000 cubic feet room)	Control cfu/m ³	1 st hr. cfu/m ³	2 nd hr. cfu/m ³	3 rd hr. cfu/m ³	4 th hr. cfu/m ³	5 th hr. cfu/m ³	6 th hr. cfu/m ³	7 th hr. cfu/m ³	8 th hr. cfu/m ³	9 th hr. cfu/m ³	10 th hr. cfu/m ³
Mean + SEM	1782.0±30.3	611.4±19.0	476.1±26.6	310.1±43.0	65.5±7.6	100.4±11.6	139.7±15.7	179.0±11.6	196.5±7.6	214.0±15.7	231.5±11.6
Fumigation effect in Percentage	0.0	65.70%	73.30%	42.20%	96.30%	94.40%	92.20%	90.00%	89.00%	88.00%	87.00%
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Viable Fungal load CFU/m ³ (Mean ± SEM)											
Sample Site (1000 cubic feet room)	Control cfu/m ³	1 st hr. cfu/m ³	2 nd hr. cfu/m ³	3 rd hr. cfu/m ³	4 th hr. cfu/m ³	5 th hr. cfu/m ³	6 th hr. cfu/m ³	7 th hr. cfu/m ³	8 th hr. cfu/m ³	9 th hr. cfu/m ³	10 th hr. cfu/m ³
Mean + SEM	91.7±7.6	61.1±4.4	30.6±4.4	13.1±0.0	4.4±4.4	8.7±14.4	13.1±0.0	13.1±0.0	17.5±4.4	17.5±4.4	17.5±4.4
Fumigation effect in Percentage	0.0	33.30 %	66.70%	85.70%	95.20%	90.50%	85.70%	85.70%	80.90%	80.90%	80.90%
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001

Fig. 5 The Impact of Exposure Time of Dhoopa Formulation-I (DF-I) through Fumigation at different Time Intervals (1to10 hrs.) in 1000 cubic feet area of room, demonstrating a Reduction of Mean Viable Bacterial and Fungal Colony Count CFU/m³ and Dhoopa Formulation-I (DF-I), Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM; *p<0.05; **p<0.002; *p< 0.001, Dhoopa fumigation effect significant from 1sthr. to 10thhr. by repeated measures, One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s multiple comparisons test.**

4.3 Impact of Exposure Time (1 to 10 hours) of Dhoopa Formulation-II (DF-II) on Bacterial Load

The Impact of Exposure Time of Dhoopa Formulation-II (DF-II) was evaluated through Fumigation with different Time Intervals (1hr. to 10hr.) in a 1000 cubic feet area of room, demonstrating a significant reduction statistically (P < 0.001) in both bacterial and fungal colony

counts (CFU/m³). Pre-fumigation controls showed a mean bacterial colony count of 1127±30.3 CFU/m³ and a fungal colony count of 104.8±7.6 CFU/m³. Following Dhoopa treatment, bacterial counts progressively decreased to 436.8±34.1 (1st hr.), 314.5±15.1 (2nd hr.), 209.6±27.3 (3rd hr.), 78.6±7.6 CFU/m³ (4th hr.), 144.1±7.6 (5th hr.), 174.7±4.4 (6th hr.), 240.2±11.6 (7th hr.), 288.3±15.1 (8th hr.), 371.3±24.3 (9th hr.) and, 432.4±27.3 (10th hr.) CFU/m³ representing the highest reduction at 4th hr. (fumigation effect

93.00%). Similarly, fungal counts declined to 69.87±15.7 (1st hr.), 39.3±7.6 (2nd hr.), 26.2±7.6 (3rd hr.), 4.4±4.4 CFU/m³ (4th hr.), 8.7±14.4 CFU/m³ (5th hr.), 13.1±0.0 CFU/m³ (6th hr.), 17.47±4.4 CFU/m³ (7th hr.), 17.5±4.4 CFU/m³ (8th

hr.), 17.5±4.4 CFU/m³ (9th hr.) and 30.6±4.4 CFU/m³ (10th hr.) achieving the highest reduction at 4th hr. (fumigation effect 95.83%). as shown in Table 6, Fig.6 Graph (A) & (B), Fig.7.

Table 6 Impact of Exposure Time (1 to 10 hours) of DF-II on Bacterial and Fungal Load

Fumigating Agent Dhooa Formulation (DF-II)											
Viable Bacterial load CFU/m ³ (Mean ± SEM)											
Sample Site (1000 cubic feet room)	Control cfu/m ³	1 st hr. cfu/m ³	2 nd hr. cfu/m ³	3 rd hr. cfu/m ³	4 th hr. cfu/m ³	5 th hr. cfu/m ³	6 th hr. cfu/m ³	7 th hr. cfu/m ³	8 th hr. cfu/m ³	9 th hr. cfu/m ³	10 th hr. cfu/m ³
Mean ± SEM	1127±30.3	436.8±34.1	314.5±15.1	209.6±27.3	78.6±7.6	144.1±7.6	174.7±4.4	240.2±11.6	288.3±15.1	371.3±24.3	432.4±27.3
Fumigation effect in Percentage	0.0	61.20%	72.10%	81.40%	93.00%	87.20%	84.50%	78.70%	74.40%	67.10%	61.60%
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Viable Fungal load CFU/m ³ (Mean ± SEM)											
Sample Site (1000 cubic feet room)	Control cfu/m ³	1 st hr. cfu/m ³	2 nd hr. cfu/m ³	3 rd hr. cfu/m ³	4 th hr. cfu/m ³	5 th hr. cfu/m ³	6 th hr. cfu/m ³	7 th hr. cfu/m ³	8 th hr. cfu/m ³	9 th hr. cfu/m ³	10 th hr. cfu/m ³
Mean ± SEM	104.8±7.6	69.87±15.7	39.3±7.6	26.2±7.6	4.4±4.4	8.7±4.4	13.1±0.0	17.47±4.4	17.5±4.4	17.5±4.4	30.6±4.4
Fumigation effect in Percentage	0	33.33 %	62.50%	75.00%	95.83%	91.67%	87.50%	83.30%	83.33%	83.33%	70.83%
P-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001

Fig. 6 The Impact of Exposure Time of Dhooa Formulation-II (DF-II) through Fumigation at different Time Intervals (1to10 hrs.) in 1000 cubic feet area of room, demonstrating a Reduction of Mean Viable Bacterial and Fungal Colony Count CFU/m³ and Dhooa Formulation-II (DF-II), Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM; *p<0.05; **p<0.002; *p< 0.001, Dhooa fumigation effect significant from 1st to 10thhr. by repeated measures, One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s multiple comparisons test**

Fig.7 Antibacterial and Antifungal efficacy of Dhoopa Formulations (DF-I & DF-II) on Nutrient Agar (NA) & Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) Plates with Time Intervals

4. DISCUSSION

The present study confirms that indoor air contains a large number of microorganisms, some of which may be harmful to human health. Effective control of these airborne microbes is therefore important for preventing the spread of infections [16]. Traditional Ayurvedic practices such as *Dhoopana* and *Havana* have historically been used for this purpose, and our findings support their scientific basis [4]. In this study, two herbal Dhoopa formulations (DF-I and DF-II) were prepared

using natural ingredients, which have been previously reported to inhibit bacterial and fungal growth, and their combination in fumigation enhances the overall antimicrobial effect [17]. The results showed that both the intensity of fumigation (amount of Dhoopa used) and the duration of exposure played important roles in determining the effectiveness of microbial reduction. When different concentrations were tested, the maximum reduction in microbial counts, bacterial colony count $34.9 \pm 4.4 \text{ CFU/m}^3$ (4th hr.), and fungal colony count $8.7 \pm 4.4 \text{ CFU/m}^3$

(4th hr.) was achieved in 10 g concentration at 4 hr of fumigation. Increasing the concentration beyond 10 g or extending the time beyond 4 hours did not show significant additional benefits, suggesting that 10 g for 4 hours is the optimal condition. Both DF-I and DF-II were highly effective, showing more than 90% Fumigation Effect in bacterial and fungal colonies. DF-I showed a maximum reduction of 65.5 ± 7.6 CFU/m³ (fumigation effect 96.30%) in bacterial and 4.4 ± 4.4 CFU/m³ (fumigation effect 95.20%) in fungal colony counts, at 4th hr. DF-II showed a maximum reduction of 78.6 ± 7.6 CFU/m³ (fumigation effect 93.00%) and 4.4 ± 4.4 CFU/m³ (fumigation effect 95.83%) for bacterial and fungal colony counts, respectively, at 4th hr. Specifically, DF-I produced a stronger reduction in bacterial colonies, while DF-II showed slightly higher activity against fungal colonies. This indicates that although both formulations are effective, their antimicrobial strengths may vary slightly depending on the type of microorganism. Overall, the findings demonstrate that herbal fumigation can provide sustained and significant antimicrobial activity, making it a safe and natural alternative for indoor air disinfection. The fact that maximum microbial load reduction was observed at the 4th hour highlights the importance of exposure time in fumigation practices. These results also suggest that the traditional practice of Dhoopana has strong scientific relevance and can be effectively applied in modern settings to reduce microbial contamination in enclosed spaces.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study confirms that Dhoopa Formulations (DF-I and DF-II) are effective in lowering airborne microbial load within indoor spaces. Prepared from natural ingredients with proven antimicrobial activity, both formulations produced significant and sustained reductions in

bacterial and fungal counts. The greatest effect was observed at a concentration of 10 g at 4 hour of fumigation, emphasizing the critical role of both intensity and exposure time. Overall, these results scientifically support the traditional Ayurvedic practice of Dhoopana and indicate that herbal fumigation offers a safe, natural, and efficient approach for long-lasting indoor air disinfection.

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Declarations

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest to disclose.

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Author's Contribution

Jyoti Sharma: Conceptualization, Validation, Data curation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, **Ajay Kumar Ahirwar:** Investigation, Software, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – review & editing **Ravi Kant Agrawal** and **Dr. Vinod Kumar Sewariya:** Writing – review & editing **Dr. Suman Jain:** Supervision, Visualization, Resources, Writing– review & editing.

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